

Model syntax and priors for model M1-M7

1. M1-M3

```
prior1 <- list(  
  B = list(mu = rep(0, 18), V = diag(18) * 1e+10), # Prior for fixed effects  
  G = list(G1 = list(V = diag(3), nu = 3, alpha.mu=rep(0,3), alpha.V=diag(3)*1000)),  
  R = list(V = diag(3), fix=3, nu = 2.002) # Prior for residual  
)
```

```
prior2 <- list(  
  B = list(mu = rep(0, 33), V = diag(33) * 1e+10), # Prior for fixed effects  
  G = list(G1 = list(V = diag(3), nu = 3, alpha.mu=rep(0,3), alpha.V=diag(3)*1000)),  
  R = list(V = diag(3), fix=3, nu = 2.002) # Prior for residual  
)
```

```
prior3 <- list(  
  B = list(mu = rep(0, 42), V = diag(42) * 1e+10), # Prior for fixed effects  
  G = list(G1 = list(V = diag(3), nu = 3, alpha.mu=rep(0,3), alpha.V=diag(3)*1000)),  
  R = list(V = diag(3), fix=3, nu = 2.002) # Prior for residual  
)
```

```
formula1 <- cbind(log.dNdS, log.prop, busted_positive) ~ trait - 1 + trait:Type +  
trait:median_length + trait:FPKM_category + trait:RSA + trait:inter
```

```
formula2 <- cbind(log.dNdS, log.prop, busted_positive) ~ trait - 1 + trait:Class +  
trait:median_length + trait:FPKM_category + trait:RSA + trait:inter
```

```
formula3 <- cbind(log.dNdS, log.prop, busted_positive) ~ trait - 1 + trait:Class +  
trait:median_length + trait:FPKM_category + trait:RSA + trait:inter
```

#Example run

```
model <- MCMCglmm(  
  formula,  
  random = ~us(trait):group,  
  rcov = ~us(trait):units,
```

```

family = c("gaussian", "gaussian", "threshold"),
prior = prior,
data = df,
nitt = 2100000,
burnin = 100000,
thin = 100,
pr = TRUE
)

```

2. M4-M6

```

prior4 <- list(
  B = list(mu = rep(0, 12), V = diag(12) * 1e+10), # Prior for fixed effects
  G = list(G1 = list(V = diag(2), nu = 2, alpha.mu=rep(0,2), alpha.V=diag(2)*1000)),
  R = list(V = diag(2), fix=2, nu = 2.002) # Prior for residual
)

```

```

prior5 <- list(
  B = list(mu = rep(0, 22), V = diag(22) * 1e+10), # Prior for fixed effects
  G = list(G1 = list(V = diag(2), nu = 2, alpha.mu=rep(0,2), alpha.V=diag(2)*1000)),
  R = list(V = diag(2), fix=2, nu = 2.002) # Prior for residual
)

```

```

prior6 <- list(
  B = list(mu = rep(0, 28), V = diag(28) * 1e+10), # Prior for fixed effects
  G = list(G1 = list(V = diag(2), nu = 2, alpha.mu=rep(0,2), alpha.V=diag(2)*1000)),
  R = list(V = diag(2), fix=2, nu = 2.002) # Prior for residual
)

```

```

formula4 <- cbind(log.lambda, is.variable) ~ trait - 1 + trait:Type + trait:median_length +
trait:FPKM_category + trait:RSA + trait:inter

```

```

formula5 <- cbind(log.lambda, is.variable) ~ trait - 1 + trait:Class + trait:median_length +
trait:FPKM_category + trait:RSA + trait:inter

```

```
formula6 <- cbind(log.lambda, is.variable) ~ trait - 1 + trait:Path + trait:median_length +
trait:FPKM_category + trait:RSA + trait:inter
```

```
#Example run
```

```
model <- MCMCglmm(
  formula,
  random = ~us(trait):group,
  rcov = ~us(trait):units,
  family = c("gaussian", "threshold"),
  prior = prior,
  data = df_lambda,
  nitt = 2100000,
  burnin = 100000,
  thin = 100,
  pr = TRUE
)
```

3. M7

```
prior7 <- list(
  B = list(mu = rep(0, 30), V = diag(30) * 1e+10), # Prior for fixed effects
  G = list(G1 = list(V = diag(5), nu = 5, alpha.mu=rep(0,5), alpha.V=diag(5)*1000)),
  R = list(V = diag(5), fix=5, nu = 2.002) # Prior for residual
)
```

```
model7 <- MCMCglmm(
  cbind(log.dNdS, log.lambda, is.variable, log.prop, busted_positive) ~ trait - 1 +
  trait:Type + trait:median_length + trait:FPKM_category + trait:RSA + trait:inter,
  random = ~us(trait):group,
  rcov = ~us(trait):units,
  family = c("gaussian", "gaussian", "threshold", "gaussian", "threshold"),
  prior = prior,
  data = df,

  nitt = 2100000,
```

```
burnin = 100000,
```

```
thin = 100,
```

```
pr = TRUE
```

```
)
```